

New Way to Think about the Feynman Path Integrations – 8 Theory

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the second main equation of the 8-theory, i.e. the primorial series of coupling constants, which regard bosonic fields as ripples or net curvature on the manifold, it is possible to construct a new way to think and visualize the Feynman diagrams. The emphasis on this paper is oriented toward broad analysis of nature and not toward actual numerical calculations.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

Photons were proven ripples on our manifold. Therefore, in construction of the new Feynman diagrams we should not regard the photons as particles but as mere distributions on the matrix. Such a construction makes it easier to understand how can a photon get into the two slits, as it is a distribution in space, not a singular entity or a particle.

Endless number of photonic ripple distributions are than subject to interference, which we defined as ripples intersecting on the same area. Such a construction was described in the coupling constants primorial function as additional net variation causing the shifting to spin of a fermion.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N2 + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = 2N2 + \frac{3}{2}$$

According to the new framework, we can verify and actually shade light on the mystery of light. Light is ripples, which are distributions of curvature on the matric space.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.14)$$

And as a distribution it can't be pinpointed to a certain trajectory, so in that case every path must be taken into account, including very weird and unlikely paths. In agreement of the Feynman path integrations principle. In the 8- theory the purpose was never to calculate the actual probability, but rather to understand why things are the way they are. The primorial function than and the new insight about bosonic ripples allow us to understand and visualize the nature of QED in a simple and elegant manner – propagation, wave particle duality due to spin varying in half a unit by additional photon, path integrations as curvature ripple distributions, it's all within 8T domain of description.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)